

Original data for visual appearance of postharvest peaches

Original data for callose deposition

Original data for Y2H screening

Original data for Y2H

Original data for luciferase complementation imaging (LCI)

Original data for coimmunoprecipitation (co-IP)

Anti-GFP
M: Prestained protein ladder maker
1: Input: *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpNPR1-CAM*
2: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpNPR1-CAM*
3: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*
4:IP:myc *PpNPR1-CAM*
5: Input: *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpMAPK1-CAM*
6: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpMAPK1-CAM*
7: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*
8:IP:myc *PpMAPK1-CAM*

Anti-myc
M: Prestained protein ladder maker
1: Input: *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpNPR1-CAM*
2: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpNPR1-CAM*
3: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*
4:IP:myc *PpNPR1-CAM*

Anti-myc
M: Prestained protein ladder maker
1: Input: *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpMAPK1-CAM*
2: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*+ *PpMAPK1-CAM*
3: IP:GFP *PpMADS2-GFP*
4:IP:myc *PpMAPK1-CAM*

Original data for subcellular localization

Original data for Y1H

Original data for four-week-old transgenic and wild-type seedlings

Original data for the representative leaves of Col-0 seedling and overexpressors after inoculation with *R. stolonifer* conidia

Original data for the representative leaves of Col-0 seedling and overexpressors after trypan blue staining

Original data for four-week-old knockout lines and wild-type seedling

Original data for the representative leaves of Col-0 seedling and knockout lines after inoculation with *R. stolonifer* conidia

Original data for the representative leaves of Col-0 seedling and knockout lines after trypan blue staining

